

The Effect of Halftoning on the Appearance of 3D Printed Surfaces

Fereshteh Abedini¹, Sasan Gooran¹ and Daniel Nyström¹

¹Media and Information Technology Division, Department of Science and Technology, Linköping University, Norrköping, Sweden.

fereshteh.abedini@liu.se; sasan.gooran@liu.se; daniel.nystrom@liu.se

Short Abstract

Managing the final appearance of 3D surfaces is an interesting and essential topic in 3D printing applications. Knowledge about the parameters which influence the 3D surface reproduction quality enables engineers to achieve the final appearance as accurately as designed. Many studies have been conducted to explore numerous parameters that affect the quality of 3D surface reproduction. This work contributes to verifying the role of halftoning in increasing the 3D surface visual quality and the control over the surface appearance of a 3D printed object. The results show that applying different halftones according to the geometrical characteristics of the 3D surface could emphasize or diminish the perceived 3D geometrical structures of a shape. The experimental results are in line with the simulated outputs reported in previous work. Our findings might introduce a new approach towards having more control over 3D appearance reproduction without changing the material or printer settings.

Keywords: 3D printing, Halftoning, Surface appearance.

1. Introduction and background

Printing devices have a limited number of inks which makes it difficult to reproduce images as accurately as desired; thus, continuous tone images should be halftoned prior to printing. Digital halftoning is a technique to reproduce different shades of colours using only limited number of inks. Halftoning leverages the fact that the human eye performs as a low pass filter and small dots are not visible to the eye from a normal viewing distance. Therefore, halftoning algorithms provide methods to optimally place dots in a way that the quantization error is shifted to a higher frequency which is not visible to the human eye.

In 2D printing, digital halftoning plays a crucial role in creating visually pleasant results. In order to improve print quality, different halftoning techniques have been developed for conventional 2D printing. Screening, error diffusion, and iterative methods are the three main categories of 2D halftoning. Studies have shown that halftoning has a constructive impact on the visual quality in printing. Screening halftoning methods are based on a threshold comparison. Therefore, they are computationally simple, but the resulting outputs suffer from several artifacts. Error diffusion and its different improved versions generate results of higher quality than screening, but still, they exhibit some artifacts in the output. Compared to screening and error diffusion, iterative halftoning methods create results of the highest quality at the cost of computational complexity.

Like in 2D printing, halftoning plays an important role in enhancing the quality of surface reproduction in 3D printing applications. However, compared to 2D printing, it still requires more development. Most of the existing 3D halftoning algorithms are extensions of their 2D counterparts, i.e., the main idea of 3D halftoning methods has been borrowed from the 2D halftoning approaches. In 2D halftoning the neighbouring pixels lie on a 2D plane, while in 3D halftoning the neighbourhood voxels form a 3D surface. As a result, the neighbourhood processing in 3D halftoning is more complex compared to 2D halftoning.

Brunton et al. (2015) introduced a novel traversal algorithm to adapt 2D error diffusion to the 3D domain. Mao et al. (2017) developed 3D DBS (Direct Binary Search) halftoning algorithm based on the 2D DBS which can be used with available 3D printing technology to reproduce 3D surfaces. Abedini et

al. (2020) have extended a search-based 2D halftoning algorithm called IMCDP (Iterative Method Controlling the Dot Placement) to the 3D domain. The aforementioned 3D halftoning methods rely on the main idea of their 2D versions, however, the researchers have modified the way of choosing the neighbouring voxels and assigning weights to them to adapt them to 3D surfaces.

Emerging 3D printing technology has paved the way towards reproduction of complex 3D surfaces. One of the crucial tasks in graphical 3D printing applications is to control the appearance of the printed objects in order to reproduce 3D surfaces as accurately as designed. Many researchers have focused on different approaches to improve the visual quality of 3D surface reproduction and create surfaces with customizable and controllable appearance.

Some recent works have focused on controlling the roughness as one of the 3D surfaces' attributes which contributes to the appearance. Roughness is introduced to the surface due to the layered manufacturing process of 3D printing. Luongo et al. (2020) studied the use of greyscale patterns to change and control the roughness of the 3D printed parts with a DLP printer. In (Ahn et al., 2009) and (Wang et al., 2019) the authors investigated the effect of printing parameters such as nozzle temperature, layer thickness, surface orientation, platform temperature, printing speed, print direction, etc. on generating surface roughness in an FDM process. They have shown that controlling printing settings and material properties are parameters that affect the appearance of the reproduced surfaces.

The authors in (Gooran and Abedini, 2020) have introduced halftoning as a parameter that could affect the appearance of the reproduced surfaces. It has been shown that it is possible to vary the resulting surface appearance of 3D objects by applying different halftone patterns onto the 3D surface. They argued that halftoning a 3D surface according to its 3D geometrical structure and the structure of the texture being mapped on it affects the visual quality of the surface reproduction.

In the current work, the goal is to validate the effect of halftoning on the final surface appearance of the 3D shapes reported in previous work (Gooran and Abedini, 2020). We utilized a 3D colour printer to apply halftones with different dot sizes and alignments on the 3D shape. The aim is to control the 3D surface appearance by using different halftone patterns while considering the 3D geometrical characteristics of the shape.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1 Methodology

Among different halftoning methods, iterative algorithms reproduce results of the highest quality. IMCDP is an iterative halftoning technique that has been proposed in (Gooran, 2004) and has been extended to the 3D domain in (Abedini et al., 2020).

2D IMCDP starts with a blank image the same size as the original image. The algorithm searches for the position of the pixel holding the maximum value in the original image; then, a black dot (a "1") is placed at its position in the blank image. The effect of this quantization is fed back to the halftoning process by subtracting the low pass filtered version of the halftoned image from the low pass filtered version of the original image. In the next iteration, the position of the pixel with the second maximum value determines the location of the next "1" in the halftoned image. The algorithm continues until the predetermined number of black dots is placed and the halftoned image is created.

The low pass filter being used in IMCDP is a Gaussian filter as represented in Equation 1:

$$f_{1st_G}(m, n) = Ke^{-\frac{1}{2\sigma^2}\left(\frac{m^2}{k_1} + \frac{n^2}{k_2}\right)}, \quad [1]$$

where m and n denote the position of the pixel under operation and σ is the standard deviation of the Gaussian function. The parameters k_1 and k_2 decide the symmetry of the applied filter. Assigning $k_1 = k_2$ results in symmetric halftone structure while, $k_1 \neq k_2$ creates halftone structures with nonsymmetric alignments. To be more precise, setting $k_1 > k_2$ makes the clusters grow faster in the horizontal direction, while $k_1 < k_2$ makes the halftone alignment vertical. There is also the possibility of generating line halftones in other directions by rotating the filter.

Applying the filter based on Equation 1 generates first order FM halftone. In first order FM halftoning, the size of the dots is constant and different absorptances are generated by varying the frequency of distribution of the dots. In this type of halftone, the quantization error is shifted to higher frequencies and as a result, the halftones exhibit blue noise characteristics. Another important feature of IMCDP is the possibility to generate second order FM halftones with green noise properties by modifying the filter as shown in Equation 2 (Gooran and Kruse, 2015). In second order FM halftones, both the size and the frequency of dots are variable, and the quantization error is shifted to mid-high frequencies.

$$f_{2nd_G}(m, n) = K \left(e^{-\frac{1}{2\sigma_1^2}(m^2+n^2)} - e^{-\frac{1}{2\sigma_2^2}\left(\frac{m^2+n^2}{k_1+k_2}\right)} \right) \quad [2]$$

By using the filter in Equation 2, single dots are first placed homogeneously based on σ_1 , then they start to form clusters and σ_2 decides on the final size of the clustered dots ($\sigma_1 > \sigma_2$). Different choices of σ_1 and σ_2 generates halftones with different clustered dot sizes.

When extending the 2D IMCDP to the 3D domain, the original pipeline of 3D IMCDP is similar to 2D IMCDP. However, the way of applying the Gaussian filter has been modified (Abedini et al., 2020). In 3D IMCDP, the neighbouring voxels are located within a box of size $m \times m \times m$ centered at the under-operation voxel and weights are assigned to the voxels based on their 3D Euclidean distances to the central point.

It has been shown that in adapting 2D IMCDP to halftone 3D surfaces, a 2D Gaussian function outperforms a 3D function as the low pass filter (Abedini et al., 2020). This means that in 3D IMCDP, weights are generated by a 2D Gaussian filter, but the 3D Euclidean distances still determines the distribution of the weights within the voxels in a neighbourhood.

As mentioned above, it is possible to create halftones of different dot sizes, shapes, and alignments only by changing the filter parameters in 3D IMCDP. Figure 1 shows examples of different halftone patterns produced by 3D IMCDP. The 3D shape is a box with some sinusoidal structures on top with variation of the 3D geometrical structures along the x-axis. As can be seen in this figure, different halftone structures change the appearance of the image (or the texture) on the 3D shape. For example, applying halftones with line structures in x-direction (parallel to the variation of the 3D structure) attenuates the perceived 3D geometry of the shape. That is the reason that the mapped image in Figure 1.a appears to have less 3D structure. On the contrary, applying line halftones perpendicular to the variation of the 3D structure emphasizes the perceived geometry of the 3D shape in the appearance of the mapped image (Figure 1.b). Figure 1.c shows the result of symmetric first order halftoning, which does not aim to diminish or emphasize the 3D structure in the appearance of the shape.

2.2 Print setup

The goal of the current work is to evaluate the effect of using different halftone structures on the perceived appearance of 3D surfaces without changing the printer parameters or materials. A colour fused filament fabrication 3D printer, DaVinci Colour 3D printer PartPro200xTCS from XYZPRINTING was used. The DaVinci Colour 3D printer combines inkjet technology with 3D printing. It uses CMYK inkjet printing technique to apply ink to a colour-absorbing PLA filament.

Figure 1: Different possible halftones generated by IMCDP. (a) Second order halftone: $\sigma_1 = 1.3$, $\sigma_2 = 0.7$ and $k_1 = 1$ & $k_2 = 2$, (b) Second order halftone: $\sigma_1 = 1.3$, $\sigma_2 = 0.7$ and $k_1 = 2$ & $k_2 = 1$, (c) First order halftone: $\sigma = 1.3$.

It is worth mentioning that the DaVinci Colour 3D printer does not allow us to have full control on the voxel level. Therefore, we simulated a thin box with sinusoidal structures on top with constant absorptance. The 3D model has been created in Blender software. The 3D shape has been halftoned using the algorithm described in Section 2.1 with second order FM using two different clustered dot sizes and alignments using MATLAB. Then, the top view of the 3D halftoned shape has been projected on the x-y plane. The resulting 2D image has been mapped onto the top face of the 3D model using closest mapping and sent to the printer.

3. Results and Discussion

To verify the effect of halftone patterns on the perceived appearance and to compare the simulated halftone outputs with experimental results, a box with sinusoidal structures on the top face has been considered as the 3D shape. The shape with constant absorptance of 0.3 has been halftoned using the filter in Equation 2. The two extreme cases, i.e., halftones with line structure parallel and perpendicular to the 3D geometrical structures, have been examined. Figure 2 shows the halftoned 3D shapes. According to the simulation results, it can be seen that halftones with lines parallel to the variation of the 3D geometrical structure of the shape has diminished the perceived 3D structures of the shape (Figure 2.a), while using halftones with perpendicular lines has emphasized it (Figure 2.b).

Since the DaVinci Colour 3D printer does not enable voxel-wise control, the 2D projection of the top face of the simulated halftoned shape has been mapped as an image texture on the top face of the 3D model and sent to the printer. Figure 3 shows examples of the 2D projection of the shapes in Figure 2 on the x-y plane. We used low resolution bitmap images in Figure 2 and 3 to make sure that the halftone structures are clearly visible.

To have a better indication of the results, a Gaussian filter with standard deviation of 4 is applied to the halftoned shapes of Figure 2. Figure 4 illustrates the filtered version of the halftoned shapes. The parameters for the Gaussian low pass filter were found experimentally, merely to illustrate the effect, and it is not based on the printer characteristics or the actual low pass characteristics of the human visual system. Comparing the halftoned shapes represented in Figure 4, the shape to the left is perceived as more homogeneous and less structured compared to the shape to the right.

Figure 5 shows images of the resulting printouts under daylight illumination. According to our observations, different halftone structures could diminish or emphasize the perceived 3D geometrical structures of the printed surface. In Figure 5, the surface to the right has been halftoned with line patterns perpendicular to the variation of the 3D structures. Comparing to the surface in the middle, which has

been halftoned with symmetric halftone alignment, the one to the right is perceived more structured. As Figure 5 illustrates, line halftones parallel to the variation of the 3D structures reduce the perceived waviness of the printed shape. That is, the shape is perceived as less wavy or of lower frequency from right to left. This could also be interpreted as the shape is perceived as a flatter surface when being halftoned by line patterns parallel to the variation of the 3D structures. It is worth noting that the viewing angle for the real prints in Figure 5 is set to be the same viewing angle for the simulation results in Figure 2.

Moreover, to evaluate the effect of clustered dot size on changing the perception of the 3D geometrical structures, we applied halftones with smaller cluster dot size to the same 3D shape. Figure 6 shows the results for two different choices of standard deviations. In this figure, the applied halftone pattern has larger clustered dots in the pair to the left. As can be seen in Figure 6, the difference between halftones with parallel and perpendicular alignment is not easily noticeable when using smaller clusters. This means that the alignment of line halftones has less impact on the appearance of the 3D surface when the clustered dot size is smaller.

Figure 2: 3D shape, absorptance 0.3, halftoned with filter parameters as $\sigma_1 = 1.9$, $\sigma_2 = 1$ and: (a) $k_1 = 1$ & $k_2 = 3$ (line halftone parallel to the 3D structure variation), (b) $k_1 = 3$ & $k_2 = 1$ (line halftone perpendicular to the 3D structure variation).

Figure 3: 2D top face views, absorptance 0.3, halftoned with filter parameters as: $\sigma_1 = 1.9$, $\sigma_2 = 1$ and: (a) $k_1 = 1$ & $k_2 = 3$ (line halftone parallel to the 3D structure variation), (b) $k_1 = 3$ & $k_2 = 1$ (line halftone perpendicular to the 3D structure variation).

Figure 4: 3D views, low pass filtered version of halftoned shapes in Figure 2. (a) $k_1 = 1$ & $k_2 = 3$ (line halftone parallel to the 3D structure variation), (b) $k_1 = 3$ & $k_2 = 1$ (line halftone perpendicular to the 3D structure variation).

Figure 5: Print results, 3D views. Filter parameters as $\sigma_1 = 1.9$, $\sigma_2 = 1$. Left: parallel, middle: symmetric alignment, right: perpendicular halftones to the 3D structure variation.

Figure 6: Print results, 3D views. Left pair: larger clustered dot size, right pair: smaller clustered dot size. In each pair, the shape to the left is halftoned with line patterns parallel to the variation of the 3D structure and the shape to the right is halftoned with line patterns perpendicular to the variation of the 3D structure. The larger clusters have greater effect on changing the appearance of the 3D geometrical structure.

4. Conclusions

In this work, we studied the effect of halftoning on perception (or misperception) of the surface geometry of 3D printed objects. To investigate the influence of halftoning on geometric surface characteristics, halftone patterns with different structures have been applied to a 3D surface. We validated the effect of halftoning in altering the appearance of 3D geometrical structure of printed surfaces by comparing the experimental 3D prints with simulation results from previous work. The 3D printouts are similar to the simulation results. It has been shown that halftones with structures parallel to the variation of the 3D

structure of the object attenuate the perceived waviness of the 3D geometry, while halftones with perpendicular lines emphasize it. However, we have not had full control over each voxel with the available 3D printer (DaVinci Colour 3D printer), hence, we believe that the role of halftoning would be even more noticeable if different halftone patterns could be applied to the 3D printed object at a voxel level.

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References

- Abedini, F., Gooran, S., Nyström, D., 2020. 3D Halftoning based on Iterative Method Controlling Dot Placement. NIP and Digital Fabrication Conference, 2020(1), pp. 69–74, Society for Imaging Science and Technology.
- Ahn, D., Kweon, J.-H., Kwon, S., Song, J., Lee, S., 2009. Representation of surface roughness in fused deposition modeling. *Journal of Materials Processing Technology*, 209 (15-16), pp. 5593–5600, Elsevier.
- Brunton, A., Arikian, C.A., Urban, P., 2015. Pushing the Limits of 3D Color Printing: Error Diffusion with Translucent Materials. *ACM Transactions on Graphics (TOG)*, 35(1), pp. 1–13, ACM New York, NY, USA.
- Gooran, S., 2004. Dependent color halftoning: Better quality with less ink. *Journal of imaging science and technology*, 48(4), pp. 354–362, Society for Imaging Science and Technology.
- Gooran, S., Abedini, F., 2020. 3D Surface Structures and 3D Halftoning. NIP and Digital Fabrication Conference, 2020(1), pp. 75–80, Society for Imaging Science and Technology.
- Gooran, S., Kruse, B., 2015. High-speed first- and second-order frequency modulated halftoning. *Journal of Electronic Imaging*, 24(2), pp. 023016, International Society for Optics and Photonics.
- Luongo, A., Falster, V., Doest, M.B., Ribo, M.M., Eiriksson, E.R., Pedersen, D.B., Frisvad, J.R., 2020. Microstructure Control in 3D Printing with Digital Light Processing. *Computer Graphics Forum*, 39(1), pp. 347–359.
- Mao, R., Sarkar, U., Ulichney, R., Allebech, J.P., 2017. 3D Halftoning. *Electronic Imaging*, 2017(18), pp. 147–155, Society for Imaging Science and Technology.
- Wang, P., Zou, B., Ding, S., 2019. Modeling of surface roughness based on heat transfer considering diffusion among deposition filaments for FDM 3D printing heat-resistant resin. *Applied Thermal Engineering*, 161, 114064, Elsevier.